

Defining Big Data for Generalist Repositories

Big Data is the term that describes large and often heterogeneous datasets that cannot be efficiently stored or processed on any single desktop or laptop. It relies on high-performance computing, often in the cloud, that provides the processing power necessary to handle complex queries and analyses ([NNLM, 2022](#)). Big Data has rapidly advanced over the previous 10 years to become essential for developing scientific insights and promoting generalizability, and provides the foundation for artificial intelligence that will drive the next generation of scientific discovery ([National Science and Technology Council, 2024](#)).

Big Data can be characterized by different facets such as “validity” (i.e., data appropriateness) or “value” (i.e., forms of significance) ([Khan et al., 2014](#)). However, the “4 Vs” is perhaps the most recognizable framework ([Kruse et al., 2016](#)):

- Volume: Pertaining to the amount or scale of the data
- Variety: The degree to which data are homogeneous or heterogeneous
- Velocity: The speed by which data are generated, processed, and analyzed, e.g. “real-time data”
- Veracity: The level of data quality

Generalist Repositories (GRs) are by definition data agnostic as they accept data from across all disciplines and methods. GRs are designed to store large amounts of data that include multiple data types and which may not adhere to strict data structures that some domain-specific repositories require. GRs are therefore well-suited to handle the *volume* and *variety* of Big Data, and increasingly, GRs provide the tools for handling Big Data’s *velocity* and managing its *veracity*.

Given the essential nature of Big Data in today’s research, the repositories participating in the NIH-funded [Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative \(GREI\)](#) have updated their [Use Case Catalog](#) to include use cases describing how researchers may use generalist repositories and leverage their specific features and functions to share and reuse Big Data.

Considering Big Data in Generalist Repositories specifically, the GREI use cases focus on the following features and challenges:

- Total storage size of dataset and size of individual files
- Total number of files per dataset
- Frequency of data updates and versioning
- Access including upload/download speeds to/from storage infrastructure and to support analysis and reuse of data
- Methods of file transfer to facilitate upload/download of data including repository APIs, FTP, Globus, etc support
- Interoperability with cloud computing and storage platforms (e.g., through Globus transfer)
- Data packaging solutions such as minimum/maximum requirements in compressed files
- Ability to create metadata only repository records that link persistently to files stored elsewhere
- Moderated access to big data infrastructure
- Curation support to ensure packaging of data supports big data
- Retention period and access levels during and following that period (e.g., full access, cold storage)
- Costs for Big Data storage, egress, and support services for repositories and institutions to ensure a sustainable data repository ecosystem
- Costs for Big Data sharing and reuse for researchers and funders for data access and use over time

For many of these features, please also see the GREI resources: [Generalist Repository Comparison Chart](#) and [Generalist Repository Selection Flowchart](#) for descriptions of repository features supporting Big Data including standard storage limits and additional free and paid offerings for larger datasets.

Sources

This definition was developed from a number of sources on Big Data. To learn more about Big Data we recommend the following resources which are either cited directly or that inform our use cases more generally.

- Kruse C., Goswamy R., Raval Y., & Marawi S. (2016). Challenges and Opportunities of Big Data in Health Care: A Systematic Review. *JMIR Medical Informatics*, 4(4), e38. <https://doi.org/10.2196/medinform.5359>
- Khan, M. A., Uddin, M. F., & Gupta, N. (2014). Seven V's of Big Data understanding Big Data to extract value. *Proceedings of the 2014 Zone 1 Conference of the American Society for Engineering Education*, Bridgeport, CT, United States, 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ASEEZone1.2014.6820689>
- Leonelli, S. (2020). Scientific Research and Big Data. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Summer 2020 Edition). Stanford University. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2020/entries/science-big-data/>
- National Science And Technology Council (NSTC). (2024). *Innovating The Data Ecosystem: An Update Of The Federal Big Data Research And Development Strategic Plan*. <https://www.nitrd.gov/pubs/Big-Data-Strategic-Plan-2024.pdf>
- Network of the National Library of Medicine (NNLM). (2022). Big Data. In *Data Glossary*. <https://www.nlm.gov/guides/data-glossary/big-data>

Authors

Aaron Doran, Mendeley Data

Joshua Richardson, Northwestern University

Ana Van Gulick, Figshare

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